

The Fallen Soldiers

(Inspiration from 'Flander's Fields')

The soldiers left in the earth

Are wanting to be honored.

The soldiers are bringing a torch to

Pass on to the survivors.

The soldiers are still in battle,

hearing the sound gun fires,

while watching from the trenches,

with the fallen soldiers as a memory.

They continue fighting the enemy,

bravely firing their guns.

They still remember their lost friends.

So they will continue,

fighting for their sake.

So the fallen soldier's memory,

will not be left in vain.

Shiny Star

A little light.

On an inky page.

A pretty star.

Halloween

The inky night

leads to light

of the children playing,

and sounds of candy.

And the costumes of

fright, and the costumes

ready for sight.

The Leader's Burden

The leader of the country,

with the heavy load

on his shoulder,

Needs the help of

other leaders,

that could be

a new friend.

The Cave

The cave is unknowned,

yet he goes to it.

he wants to explore it,

and find something new.

He knows it is dangerous.

but he also knows

it will be fun.

Reading

Reading is like

an adventure.

You can climb the

mountains of a

encyclopedia.

or the soft sands

of a dictionary.

no matter what you read,

it will be an adventure.

The Fight

(Inspiration from 'A Boy Named Sue')

They fight and fight.

The brawl never ends.

The bloodshed is horrid.

All because of a name.

It makes no sense.

When we think its over,

Another fist comes,

then comes the blood,

It needs to end.

It may never end,

But hopefully it does.

Money Back

(Inspiration from 'You Don't Mess Around With Jim')

He was the strongest man,

He robbed that man.

The man wanted his money back.

So he ran and got to him

He beat him until he fell.

When he fell, he was dead.

He got his money back

The Duel

(Inspiration from the Alexander Hamilton-Aaron Burr duel from 'Hamilton')

There was two men,

Who didn't like each other.

They had a duel.

It wasn't fair.

The evil one had cheated.

He fired at the count of two.

The man with the family,

Was no longer alive.

Now there was just one man.

After the War

The war was over,

Only one hundred thousand men came back,

It is sad.

So many came into war as fathers,

Now only these men come back as heroes.

But why so many men dead.

Lost Time

(Inspiration from 'Cat's in the Cradle')

He tried to spend
Some time with his dad,
But his dad had no time,
He had to work all day.
But ten years later, he
Regretted all the lost time.
His son said how
He loved his dad.
His dad wept into tears.
He said I love you too.
They spent time together,
But eventually he had to go.
ten years later he wept at his grave.

The Son's Father

A father had to leave his

Son because of war.

He didn't want to go

But he had to.

six months later, there was

Still nothin' known.

five years later, they got a call.

He wept into tears.

He missed his dad.

Stories' Villain

Every story needs a villain,
It may not be actually true,
It's just for the story,
Its for the fun

The Pool Man

(inspiration from 'You Don't Mess Around With Jim')

He was a master of pool,

Nobody could beat him,

He met a gambler,

That just hit a jackpot.

He beat him up,

He got the money,

The robbed man

Got him back.

Ran Away

(Inspiration from 'You Don't Mess Around With Jim' and 'Bad, Bad, Leroy Brown')

He got his money

From the pool man.

He ran away,

He got really far.

He changed his name,

He got really famous,

He was the toughest

Guy in the whole town.

He lived an extravagant life.

The Pool Hustler's Brother

(Inspiration from 'Bad, Bad, Leroy Brown')

He met a guy who was

The brother of the pool hustler.

He wanted to get his revenge.

He towards him,

He thought he could win,

But he was doomed from the start.

Guy From Alabama

The guy from Alabama

Went up north.

He talked to someone

And they asked were you from

He said from Alabama.

He was lost for ten days

He came back

He Found A Girl

(Inspiration From 'Roller Derby Queen')

A few years later

After he changed his name,

He met a girl he liked.

They got married,

And they had a child.

In Old Age

Now than man that
Killed the pool hustler,
Is now in old age,
He watched his son grow up
And have children.
He lived for one hundred twenty years,
He saw his descendants
To the fourth generation
He died full of strength
He could continue,
Yet he didn't.